

A modified type of Fletcher-Reeves conjugate gradient method with its global convergence

Amna Weis Mohammed Ahmad Idress¹, Osman Omer Osman Yousif¹, Abdulgader Zaid Almaymuni²,
Awad Abdelrahman Abdalla Mohammed¹, Mohammed A. Saleh², Nafisa A. Ali¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical and Computer Sciences, University of Gezira, Wad Medani, Sudan

²Department of Computer, College of Science and Arts in Ar Rass, Qassim University, Ar Rass, Saudi Arabia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Nov 8, 2022

Revised Nov 7, 2023

Accepted Nov 13, 2023

Keywords:

Conjugate gradient method

Exact line search

Fletcher-Reeves method

Global convergence

Unconstrained optimization

ABSTRACT

The conjugate gradient methods are one of the most important techniques used to address problems involving minimization or maximization, especially nonlinear optimization problems with no constraints at all. That is because of their simplicity and low memory needed. They can be applied in many areas, such as economics, engineering, neural networks, image restoration, machine learning, and deep learning. The convergence of Fletcher-Reeves (FR) conjugate gradient method has been established under both exact and strong Wolfe line searches. However, its performance in practice is poor. In this paper, to get good numerical performance from the FR method, a little modification is done. The global convergence of the modified version has been established for general nonlinear functions. Preliminary numerical results show that the modified method is very efficient in terms of number of iterations and CPU time.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Osman Omer Osman Yousif

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical and Computer Sciences, University of Gezira

Wad Madani, Sudan

Email: osman_om@hotmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

To determine a function's minimum, one nonlinear optimization technique is the Fletcher-Reeves conjugate gradient (FRCG) method. The FRCG technique builds a series of search directions that are conjugate to each other by using the function's gradients, which is based on the concept of conjugate gradients. The fast convergence of the FRCG approach to the function's minimum is made possible by this characteristic of conjugate gradients. Considering the following problem of unconstrained optimization;

$$\min f(x), x \in R^n, \quad (1)$$

where $f: R^n \rightarrow R$ is a smooth function with gradient g . Conjugate gradient methods are well qualified for solving (1) even if it is of large scale. They are use;

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k d_k, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad (2)$$

where α_k is the step-length taken in the direction of search d_k . The search direction is given by;

$$d_k = \begin{cases} -g_k, & \text{if } k = 0 \\ -g_k + \beta_k d_{k-1}, & \text{if } k \geq 1, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{g}_k = \nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k)$ and β_k is a real number, called conjugate gradient coefficient. Different formulas for β_k determine different conjugate gradient methods such as of Fletcher-Reeves (FR), Dai-Yuan (DY), Conjugate Descent (CD), Polak-Rebriere and Polyak (PRP), Hestenes-Stiefel (HS), Liu-Storey (LS). Fletcher [1], Dai and Yuan [2], Fletcher [3], Polyak [4] and Polak and Rebriere [5], Hestenes and Stiefel [6] and Liu and Storey [7] whose coefficients are respectively given by;

$$\beta_k^{\text{FR}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k-1}\|^2}$$

$$\beta_k^{\text{DY}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2}{\mathbf{d}_{k-1}^T (\mathbf{g}_k - \mathbf{g}_{k-1})}$$

$$\beta_k^{\text{CD}} = -\frac{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2}{\mathbf{d}_{k-1}^T \mathbf{g}_{k-1}}$$

$$\beta_k^{\text{PRP}} = \frac{\mathbf{g}_k^T (\mathbf{g}_k - \mathbf{g}_{k-1})}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k-1}\|^2}$$

$$\beta_k^{\text{HS}} = \frac{\mathbf{g}_k^T (\mathbf{g}_k - \mathbf{g}_{k-1})}{\mathbf{d}_{k-1}^T (\mathbf{g}_k - \mathbf{g}_{k-1})}$$

$$\beta_k^{\text{LS}} = -\frac{\mathbf{g}_k^T (\mathbf{g}_k - \mathbf{g}_{k-1})}{\mathbf{d}_{k-1}^T \mathbf{g}_{k-1}}$$

the step-length α_k can be evaluated using the exact search, in which;

$$f(\mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k \mathbf{d}_k) = \min f(\mathbf{x}_k + \alpha \mathbf{d}_k), \alpha \geq 0. \quad (4)$$

Since the computation of α_k using (4) is so hard in practice, other methods for computing the step length α_k are defined. These methods are called inexact line searches. An example of the inexact method which is used widely in practice is the Wolfe, in which the step length satisfies the conditions;

$$f(\mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k \mathbf{d}_k) - f(\mathbf{x}_k) \leq \delta \alpha_k \mathbf{g}_k^T \mathbf{d}_k \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k \mathbf{d}_k)^T \geq \sigma \mathbf{g}_k^T \mathbf{d}_k \quad (6)$$

where $0 < \delta < \sigma < 1$.

Another strong version of Wolfe is the strong Wolfe, given by (5) and (7);

$$|\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_k + \alpha_k \mathbf{d}_k)^T \mathbf{d}_k| \leq \delta |\mathbf{g}_k^T \mathbf{d}_k| \quad (7)$$

to ensure that the search for the solution of the problem in (1) is in the correct direction, the direction is imposed to be descent. So, the descent of \mathbf{d}_k (downhill condition) has a great role in the conjugate gradient methods. The (8) of the descent of \mathbf{d}_k occurs from the inequality;

$$\mathbf{g}_k^T \mathbf{d}_k < 0, \quad (8)$$

which can be extended to the so-called the sufficient descent criterion;

$$-\mathbf{g}_k^T \mathbf{d}_k \geq c \|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2, c > 0. \quad (9)$$

Conjugate gradient methods are still the best choice for solving (1). Over the years, for better performance, many efforts have been devoted to define new methods and to modify others such as the studies in [8]–[17]. The FR conjugate gradient method has rich convergence properties. However, its numerical performance is much slower than that of many others. Zoutendijk [18] reported that, the FR method via exact line search converges globally on general functions. Later, Al-Baali [19] has proven this result via strong Wolfe.

Recently, to establish the convergence properties and to obtain good numerical performance in practice, remarkable efforts have been dedicated to upgrade new versions and to modify well-known methods. For example, the modification of the PRP and the HS methods via exact and strong Wolfe line searches [20]–[22]

and the proof of the global convergence of Rivaia-Mamat-Ismail-Leong modified method (RMIL+) via the strong wolfe [23]. In this article, for better numerical results of FR method in practice, we present a modified FR method which is again globally convergent and of better performance in practice than the FR.

2. THE PROPOSED METHOD AND ALGORITHM

Motivated by the global convergence of the FR, we made a little change to its formula to obtain a modified version with global convergence and better numerical results. The modified formula is given by;

$$\beta_k^{WFR} = \frac{\|g_k\|^2}{\|g_{k-1}\| \|d_{k-1}\|} \tag{10}$$

where the letter W stands for Weis, the family name of the first author.

Having a new formula in (10), we get a new conjugate gradient method called WFR and can be described in the following algorithm 1;

Algorithm 1. WFR algorithm

- Step 1. Initialization, choose $x_0 \in R^n, \varepsilon \geq 0$, let $d_0 = -g_0$, and $k = 0$.
- Step 2. If $\|g_k\| \leq \varepsilon$, then terminate.
- Step 3. Compute α_k using (4).
- Step 4. Set $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k d_k$, and $g_{k+1} = g(x_{k+1})$. If $\|g_{k+1}\| \leq \varepsilon$, terminate.
- Step 5. Evaluate β_k using (10) and d_k using (3).
- Step 6. Put $k = k + 1$ and go to Step 3.

3. GLOBAL CONVERGENCE OF THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The convergence analysis plays an important role when studing conjugate gradient method. In this section, we establish the convergence of Algorithm 1. Firstly, we assume the following assumptin on f.

3.1. Assumption

- f is bounded below on the set $\{x \in R^n: f(x) \leq f(x_0)\}$.
- In some neighboring \mathcal{N} of the set in (i), f(x) is differentiable and its g is Lipschitz continuous, namely, there exists a constant $\mu > 0$ such that;

$$\|g(x) - g(y)\| \leq \mu \|x - y\| \quad \forall x, y \in \mathcal{N}$$

By considering assumption 3.1, the following Zoutendijk [18] condition refer to Zoutendijk [18] holds;

$$\sum_{k=0} \cos^2 \theta_k \|g_k\|^2 < \infty$$

where θ_k is the angle between d_k and the steepest descent direction $-g_k$.

Observe that the Zoutendijk [18] condition implies;

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \cos^2 \theta_k \|g_k\|^2 = 0$$

to establish the global convergence, we prove;

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|g_k\| = 0 \tag{11}$$

hence, if $\cos^2 \theta_k \geq \delta > 0$, then (11) is hold true.

In exact line search, the orthogonality condition;

$$g_k^T d_{k-1} = 0 \tag{12}$$

holds for all k. from (12) and (3), we get;

$$g_k^T d_k = -\|g_k\|^2 + \beta_k g_k^T d_{k-1} = -\|g_k\|^2 \tag{13}$$

hence, since $\mathbf{g}_k^T \mathbf{d}_k = \|\mathbf{g}_{k-1}\| \|\mathbf{d}_{k-1}\| \cos \theta_{k-1}$, we get;

$$\cos \theta_{k-1} = \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_{k-1}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k-1}\| \|\mathbf{d}_{k-1}\|} \quad (14)$$

substituting (14) into the formula (10), we get;

$$\beta_k^{WFR} = \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k-1}\|^2} \cos \theta_{k-1} = \beta_k^{FR} \cos \theta_{k-1}$$

since $-1 \leq \cos \theta_{k-1} \leq 1$, we deduce that;

$$-\beta_k^{FR} \leq \beta_k^{WFR} \leq \beta_k^{FR}$$

also, substituting (14) into Zoutendijk's condition, we get;

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^4}{\|\mathbf{d}_k\|^2} < \infty \quad (15)$$

next, we set the convergence of Algorithm 2.1.

3.2. Theorem

Suppose that Assumption 3.1 is satisfied. Let $\{x_k\}$ be produced by Algorithm 1. Then Algorithm 1 is globally convergent, that is, holds true (11).

3.2.1. Proof

To prove, we use contradiction, that is, by supposing (11) is not true. Thus, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ that;

$$\|\mathbf{g}_k\| \geq \varepsilon, \text{ for all } k \quad (16)$$

from (3), indeed, \mathbf{d}_{k+1} can be displayed as;

$$\mathbf{d}_{k+1} + \mathbf{g}_{k+1} = \beta_{k+1}^{WFR} \mathbf{d}_k$$

squaring the both sides, we come to;

$$\|\mathbf{d}_{k+1}\|^2 = (\beta_{k+1}^{WFR})^2 \|\mathbf{d}_k\|^2 - 2\mathbf{g}_{k+1}^T \mathbf{d}_{k+1} - \|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2 \quad (17)$$

due to (10) and (17), we have;

$$\|\mathbf{d}_{k+1}\|^2 = \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_k\| \|\mathbf{d}_k\|} \right)^2 \|\mathbf{d}_k\|^2 - 2\mathbf{g}_{k+1}^T \mathbf{d}_{k+1} - \|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2 \quad (18)$$

using (12), we obtain;

$$\|\mathbf{d}_{k+1}\|^2 = \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^4}{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2 \|\mathbf{d}_k\|^2} \|\mathbf{d}_k\|^2 + 2\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2 - \|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2$$

which implies;

$$\|\mathbf{d}_{k+1}\|^2 = \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^4}{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2} + \frac{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^4}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2}$$

so that;

$$\|\mathbf{d}_{k+1}\|^2 = \|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^4 \left(\frac{1}{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2} + \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2} \right)$$

consequently;

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{d}_{k+1}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^4} = \left(\frac{1}{\|\mathbf{g}_k\|^2} + \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{g}_{k+1}\|^2} \right) \quad (19)$$

from (16) which means that $\frac{1}{\|g_k\|^2} \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon^2}$ together with (19), we come to;

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\|d_{k+1}\|^2}{\|g_{k+1}\|^4} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{\varepsilon^2}$$

that is,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\|g_{k+1}\|^4}{\|d_{k+1}\|^2} \geq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \tag{20}$$

inequality (20), leads to;

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\|g_{k+1}\|^4}{\|d_{k+1}\|^2} \geq \infty,$$

which contradicts (15). Therefore, the proof is completed. After proving the global convergence, it remains to show the performance in practical computations.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this part, we compare FR and WFR via exact line search and show the results Table 1 in Appendix. Table 1 in Appendix, most of the test problems are taken from Andrei [24]. Also, problem is the test problem, Dim is the dimension taken of the problem, X_0 is the initial points from the literature, NI is the number of iterations, FR is the FR method by exact line search, WFR is the modified FR method shown in Algorithm 2.1, and CT(s) is the CPU time. Now to show the improvement in WFR when it is compared with FR, we take FR as 100% with respect to number of iterations (NOI) and CPU time to obtain the following table.

Table 2. Performance of Table 1 based on NOI and CPU time

TOOLS	FR	WFR
NOI	100%	39%
CPU	100%	21%

From Table 2, we see that there is an improvement of about 61% in NOI and about 79% in CPU time. Therefore, in practical computation, WFR is much better than FR method. Also, based on Table 1, we can show the performance by considering $t_{p,s}$ is the result when a solver s is applied to solve problem p (here our solvers are FR and WFR method) and $P_s(t)$ is the ratio $\frac{t_{p,s}}{\min\{t_{p,s};s \in S\}}$ as in Dolan and More [25] profile, we show the efficiency of Algorithm 2.1 in Figures 1 and 2. Dolan and More [25] performance profile a method of high curve is the best, so it is clear from Figures 1 and 2 that, the WFR method which is described in Algorithm 1 is much better than the FR method.

Figure 1. Performance results in case of NI

Figure 2. Performance results in case of CPU time

APPENDIX

Table 1. Numerical results

Problem	Dim	X_0	FR		WFR	
			NI	CT(s)	NI	CT(s)
Extended white and holst	10	-2	882	5.0080	41	0.2632
	1,000		632	30.8033	41	2.1916
	10	6	598	3.8213	772	4.9758
Extended freudenstein and roth	100	2	16	0.1422	13	0.3207
	1,000		18	0.5242	13	0.3835
	100	4	8	0.2460	6	0.1642
Extended beale	10	6	277	3.2659	13	0.1753
	100		277	3.2565	13	0.2748
Raydan 1	10	2	408	3.6955	137	1.2304
	100		327	2.9331	120	1.1057
Extended tridiagonal 1	100	-3	197	1.7995	130	1.1991
	10	3	324	2.3845	83	0.6257
	100		511	6.2461	99	1.2157
	1,000		843	50.7911	107	6.4142
	10	9	45	0.5610	57	0.7072
	100		33	0.4116	77	0.9463
Diagonal 4 function	1,000		46	2.7753	81	4.8669
	10	2	5	0.0598	5	0.0637
Extended himmelblau	10	2	9	0.0748	8	0.0737
	1,000		10	0.2371	9	0.1996
	10	-2	19	0.4247	20	0.4534
	100		19	0.4171	19	0.4286
	10	6	15	0.3315	15	0.3291
	500		15	0.3355	15	0.3263
FLETCHCR function	1,000		15	0.3378	15	0.3280
	100	4	27	0.2303	26	0.2273
Extended DENSCHNB	100	-2	14	0.1519	13	0.1502
Extended quadratic penalty QP1	10	3	18	0.1515	14	0.1281
	100		314	2.6221	19	0.1913
	100	-2	1,466	12.4513	17	0.1587
Extended penalty	10	3	19	0.1937	15	0.1683
	100		33	0.3281	16	0.1745
	100	-2	46	0.4181	12	0.1257
Hager function	10	-2	24	0.2270	18	0.1680
	100		45	0.5284	31	0.3776
	10	-3	89	1.0508	32	0.3829
Extended maratos	100		59	0.7012	33	0.3964
	100	2	39	0.4379	38	0.3335
Shallow function	100	-2	272	4.6560	53	0.5677
	100	-2	41	0.3843	28	0.2703
	1,000		45	0.9068	28	0.5784
Generalized quartic function	1,000	2	30	0.7150	12	0.2538
	100	5	10	0.2524	10	0.2222
	500		10	0.2526	10	0.2512
	1,000		10	0.2602	10	0.2587
Quadratic QF2 function	100	2	400	3.7661	147	1.4687
	1,000	-3	24	0.5763	16	0.3916
Generlized tridiagonal 1	100	3	43	0.5983	27	0.4777
Generlized tridiagonal	10	-2	36	0.4908	29	0.3859
	10	2	22	0.2232	30	0.2862
POWER function	10	3	22	0.1971	158	1.2606
Quadratic QF1	10	2	10	0.1063	27	0.2598
Extended QP2	10	5	24	0.2363	29	0.2817
Extended quadratic penalty QP1	100	-2	283	4.3781	61	1.1500
	100	3	1,086	54.3123	49	0.6430
	500	9	1,268	62.4915	82	2.1236
Dixon and price function	10	-2	73	0.7407	71	0.6997
Sphere function	100	-2	1	0.1828	1,202	12.3998
Sum square's function	10	-2	59	0.5832	135	1.3047
	100		59	0.5789	135	1.3204
Strait function	10	5	81	0.8645	37	0.4187
ARWHEAD function	10	3	10	0.1039	10	0.2854

5. CONCLUSION

In this article, a modified version of FR is proposed. Based on the proposed formula, a new modified method is presented. The global convergence is established, provided the line search is exact. To show the

efficiency of the modified method in practice, it has been compared with the FR method. It has been reported that the new modified one is much better than FR method.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Researchers would like to thank the Deanship of Scientific Research, Qassim University for funding publication of this project.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Fletcher, "Function minimization by conjugate gradients," *The Computer Journal*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 149–154, Feb. 1964.
- [2] Y. H. Dai and Y. Yuan, "A nonlinear conjugate gradient method with a strong global convergence property," *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 177–182, Jan. 1999, doi: 10.1137/S1052623497318992.
- [3] R. Fletcher, *Practical methods of optimization*. Wiley, 2000. doi: 10.1002/9781118723203.
- [4] B. T. Polyak, "The conjugate gradient method in extremal problems," *USSR Computational Mathematics and Mathematical Physics*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 94–112, Jan. 1969, doi: 10.1016/0041-5553(69)90035-4.
- [5] E. Polak and G. Ribiere, "Note sur la convergence de méthodes de directions conjuguées," *Revue française d'informatique et de recherche opérationnelle. Série rouge*, vol. 3, no. 16, pp. 35–43, May 1969, doi: 10.1051/m2an/196903R100351.
- [6] M. R. Hestenes and E. Stiefel, "Methods of conjugate gradients for solving linear systems," *Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards*, vol. 49, no. 6, p. 409, Dec. 1952, doi: 10.6028/jres.049.044.
- [7] Y. Liu and C. Storey, "Efficient generalized conjugate gradient algorithms, part 1: theory," *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 129–137, Apr. 1991, doi: 10.1007/BF00940464.
- [8] M. Rivaie, M. Mamat, L. W. June, and I. Mohd, "A new class of nonlinear conjugate gradient coefficients with global convergence properties," *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 218, no. 22, pp. 11323–11332, Jul. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.amc.2012.05.030.
- [9] M. Rivaie, M. Mamat, and A. Abashar, "A new class of nonlinear conjugate gradient coefficients with exact and inexact line searches," *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 268, pp. 1152–1163, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.amc.2015.07.019.
- [10] L. Zhang, "An improved Wei–Yao–Liu nonlinear conjugate gradient method for optimization computation," *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 215, no. 6, pp. 2269–2274, Nov. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.amc.2009.08.016.
- [11] L. Guanghui, H. Jiye, and Y. Hongxia, "Global convergence of the fletcher-reeves algorithm with inexact linesearch," *Applied Mathematics-A Journal of Chinese Universities*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 75–82, Mar. 1995, doi: 10.1007/BF02663897.
- [12] H. Huang, Z. Wei, and Y. Shengwei, "The proof of the sufficient descent condition of the Wei–Yao–Liu conjugate gradient method under the strong wolfe–powell line search," *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 189, no. 2, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.amc.2006.12.006.
- [13] A. Abdelrahman, O. Yousif, M. Mhammed, and M. Elbashir, "Global convergence of nonlinear conjugate gradient coefficients with inexact line search," *Basic and Applied Sciences - Scientific Journal of King Faisal University*, 2021, doi: 10.37575/b/sci/210058.
- [14] Z. Dai and F. Wen, "A modified CG-DESCENT method for unconstrained optimization," *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 235, no. 11, pp. 3332–3341, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.cam.2011.01.046.
- [15] Z. Wei, S. Yao, and L. Liu, "The convergence properties of some new conjugate gradient methods," *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 183, no. 2, pp. 1341–1350, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.amc.2006.05.150.
- [16] Z.-F. Dai, "Two modified HS type conjugate gradient methods for unconstrained optimization problems," *Nonlinear Analysis: Theory, Methods & Applications*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 927–936, Feb. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.na.2010.09.046.
- [17] W. W. Hager and H. Zhang, "A new conjugate gradient method with guaranteed descent and an Efficient line search," *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 170–192, Jan. 2005, doi: 10.1137/030601880.
- [18] G. Zoutendijk, *Nonlinear programming, computational methods*, vol. 5, no. 2. Integer and Nonlinear Programming, 1970.
- [19] M. Al-Baali, "Descent property and global convergence of the fletcher-reeves method with inexact line search," *IMA Journal of Numerical Analysis*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 121–124, 1985, doi: 10.1093/imanum/5.1.121.
- [20] O. O. O. Yousif, M. A. Y. Mohammed, M. A. Saleh, and M. K. Elbashir, "A criterion for the global convergence of conjugate gradient methods under strong Wolfe line search," *Journal of King Saud University - Science*, vol. 34, no. 8, Nov. 2022.
- [21] O. Yousif, A. Abdelrahman, M. Mohammed, and M. Saleh, "A sufficient condition for the global convergence of conjugate gradient methods for solving unconstrained optimisation problems," *Basic and Applied Sciences - Scientific Journal of King Faisal University*, pp. 1–7, 2022, doi: 10.37575/b/sci/220013.
- [22] J. C. Gilbert and J. Nocedal, "Global convergence properties of conjugate gradient methods for optimization," *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 21–42, Feb. 1992, doi: 10.1137/0802003.
- [23] O. O. O. Yousif, "The convergence properties of RMIL+ conjugate gradient method under the strong Wolfe line search," *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 367, p. 124777, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.amc.2019.124777.
- [24] N. Andrei, "An unconstrained optimization test functions collection," *Advanced Modelling and Optimization*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 147–161, 2008.
- [25] E. D. Dolan and J. J. Moré, "Benchmarking optimization software with performance profiles," *Mathematical Programming*, vol. 91, no. 2, pp. 201–213, Jan. 2002, doi: 10.1007/s101070100263.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Amna Weis Mohammed Ahmad Idress is Sudanese born in Gezira province. She received her B.Ed. (Honor) in Mathematics from Faculty of Education, Hantoub, University of Gezira, Sudan. She has received her postgraduate diploma in Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical and Computer Science, University of Gezira. Also, she has M.Sc. degree in Mathematics. Now she is a Ph.D. student in the field of the optimization methods for solving unconstrained problems, especially the conjugate gradient methods. Beside optimization, her research interests include numerical computation, and operation research. She can be contacted at the email: amnaweis@gmail.com.

Osman Omer Osman Yousif is an Associate Professor at Faculty of Mathematical and Computer Sciences, University of Gezira, Sudan. He received the Ph.D. from Universiti Malaysia Terengganu (UMT) in 2015 with specialization in Optimization. He is the Head of Mathematics Department since 2019 up to now. He was also the postgraduate coordinator. He was a supervisor, a co-supervisor, and an examiner of more than 35 master students. His research interests include Optimization, Numerical Computation, and Operation Research. He has 19 publications in conference proceedings, ISI journals, and Scopus journals with 3 H-index and 65 citations. He can be contacted at email: osman.omer@uofg.edu.sd.

Dr. Abdugader Zaid Almaymuni is an associate Professor at Faculty of computer Science, university of Qassim, Saudi arabia. He received the Ph.D. from DemontFort university (UK) in 2013 with specialization in computer security and smart systems. He was the vice dean of e-learning deanship at Qassim university 2018-2022. He has more than 20 publications in conference proceedings, Journals. His research interests include cyber security, context-aware, formal method and smart systems. He can be contacted at email: Almaymuni@qu.edu.sa.

Awad Abdelrahman Abdalla Mohammed is an associate Professor in University of Gezira. He has received his Ph.D. degree in mathematical sciences from University of Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia in 2017. Also, he is now a head of the documentation committee and a member of courses development committee. He interested in optimization and computational mathematics. He supervised to undergraduate and M.Sc. students. He has participated in conferences in Malaysia, Sudan and served as a co-chair of ICCCEEE18 conference which held in Khartoum in 2018. He can be contacted at emailawad.abdalla26@yahoo.com or awadabdalla@uofg.edu.sd.

Mohammed A. Saleh was born in Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). He received the B.Sc. (Honor) in Mathematical and Computer Science, Faculty of Mathematical and Computer Science, University of Gezira, Sudan. He obtained the M.Sc. (First Class) in Information Security, Faculty of Computer Science and Information System, University of Technology (UTM), Malaysia, and the Ph.D. in Information Security (Computer Science), Faculty of Computing, University of Technology (UTM), Malaysia. From 2010 to 2014, he was a Security Engineer with the Sudanese Nation Information Center (NIC). As well, he was Lecturer at Gezira University. Currently, he is an Assistant Professor at Qassim University, KSA. His research interests include Malware Analysis and Artificial Intelligence in Cybersecurity. He is the author of a couple of journal articles. He can be contacted at email: m.saleh@qu.edu.sa.

Nafisa A. Ali is a Sudanese natunality born in Algezira province, Sudan. She is a Ph.D. student in Mathematics (Optimization) and in the same time a lecturer at the Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical and Computer Sciences, University of Gezira, Sudan. She has received her B.Sc. (Honor) in Mathematics and Computer Science from University of Gezira, Sudan. Further, her M.Sc. degree was in industrial and computational mathematics from Faculty of Mathematical Science, University of Khartoum. She supervised to many undergraduate students in the department in different area of mathematics. She can be contacted at email: nafisa@uofg.edu.sad.